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**Yield stability and performance in the LTE-OM
and LTE-Tillage in Belgium. Report related to
EJPSOIL ARTEMIS WP2**

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1. Introduction

In the context of a changing climate characterized by increasing environmental constraints and unpredictable extreme weather events such as drought, floods, heat waves, both the quantities and stability of crop production are under significant threat.

This emerging reality raises critical concerns for global food security, particularly given that crop productivity and yield stability are essential for meeting the rising global demand for food. This demand intensifies as the population grows and the availability of arable land becomes more limited. For farmers, yield stability over time is relevant, as it directly affects economic predictability and risk. Therefore, the dual objective of achieving high productivity levels and consistent yield stability is thus paramount in contemporary agricultural science.

Long-term field experiments (LTEs) offer a unique opportunity to assess effects of various cropping systems and agricultural practices, particularly concerning time-dependent parameters such as yield stability. Indeed, these experiments provide long-term data and observations that allow for the analysis of yearly variability in crop performance under fluctuating environmental conditions.

In this report, we reused data from two long-term field experiments conducted in southern Belgium that evaluate the impacts of different soil management practices. These practices include on one hand the enhancement of soil organic matter in soil through the incorporation of crop residues, the use of cover crops and the application of livestock manures) and on the other hand the implementation of different soil tillage techniques. These strategies aiming to improve soil fertility and quality, while minimizing soil disturbance through reduced tillage, we test the hypothesis that they promote the resilience of cropping systems to the stresses imposed by a changing climate.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Description of the LTEs

The Organic Matter (LTE-OM) and Tillage (LTE-Tillage) Long-Term Experiments were initiated by the Walloon Agricultural Research Center (Centre wallon de Recherches agronomiques, CRA-W) in Belgium, to meet the following objectives :

- Monitoring soil fertility and crop productivity indicators in accordance with agricultural practices :

Within the framework of an agro-ecological agriculture constrained by the contribution of mineral fertilizers, organic matter inputs and its management are key elements of the fertility of agricultural soils, in the broad sense : chemical, biological and physical fertility. Moreover soil tillage has a significant impact on soil structure, soil functionalities (mineralization of C and N) and soil fertility.

- Identifying potential agricultural practices allowing to adapt/mitigate climate change :

These experiments allow to understand the processes of carbon storage and sequestration according to the mode of management of the crop residues, cover crops, the contribution of organic amendments (manure, slurry) and the mode of soil tillage (conventional versus reduced/non-inversion tillage).

The experiments are situated next to each other in Gembloux, a town located in the silt loam region of Wallonia, southern Belgium. The climate is temperate oceanic, with an average annual temperature of 10.2°C and mean annual rainfall of 793.4 mm for the period from 1991 to 2020 (IRM, 2024). The soil is classified as a Hortic Luvisol (World reference base for soil resources, 2014) with a silt loam texture in the Ap horizon (0-25 cm), consisting of 85% silt, 12% clay, and 3% sand (Roisin, 2018).

2.1.1. LTE-OM

The LTE-OM (50.561° N, 4.726° E) was established in 1959 with the initial aim of assessing the impact of decreasing OM inputs on soil fertility, crop yields and farm profitability within the specific context of the silt loam region, where arable cropping has been progressively disconnected from cattle breeding since the second half of the 20th century.

From 1959 to 1974, the field was cultivated following a four-year crop rotation, starting with sugar beet (*Beta vulgaris* L.) followed by three winter cereals (wheat, oat, barley – *Hordeum vulgare* subsp. *hexastichum*) or two winter cereals (wheat, barley/oat) and a legume (faba bean). From 1975 onwards, a three-year crop rotation was adopted with sugar beet followed by two cereals, or occasionally one cereal and one faba bean. Finally, since 1991, the sugar beet - wheat - barley rotation has been consistently implemented.

The trial contains six contrasting treatments of OM inputs, implemented within plots measuring 72 m x 10 m. These treatments are replicated six times, following a Latin square design with the blocks aligned in a row.

The treatments compared are as follows :

- Residue Exportation (RE) - control : Export of all aboveground crop residues without any exogenous OM input
- Pig slurry + Residue restitution + Cover crop (PS + RR + CC) : input of 20 to 55 t ha⁻¹ of PS spread after the harvest of the last cereal in the crop rotation, incorporation of all aboveground crop residues and cover crop production
- Cattle Manure (CM) - business as usual : Export of all aboveground crop residues and input of 30 to 60 t ha⁻¹ of composted CM spread after the harvest of the last cereal in the crop rotation
- Residue Restitution (RR) : Incorporation of chopped cereal straws
- Residue Restitution + Cover Crop (RR + CC) : Incorporation of all aboveground crop residues and cover crop production

Note that there are two PS + RR + CC treatments, although currently considered as identical, that were extensively modified from 1975 by gradually introducing OM inputs that were more rapid in PS + RR + CC_1 than PS + RR + CC_2 (Fig. A.1).

Various cover crops have been cultivated since the start of the experiment, with vetch – *Vicia sativa* L. having been grown most frequently (13 years), followed by mustard – *Sinapis alba* L. (10 years), phacelia – *Phacelia tanacetifolia* (3 years), oilseed rape – *Brassica napus* (2 years),

oat (2 years), clover – *Trifolium alexandrinum* L. (2 years), radish – *Raphanus sativus* (1 year), and sunflower – *Helianthus annuus* (1 year). The cover crops are grown once per rotation during the intercropping period before sugar beet cultivation.

2.1.2. LTE-Tillage

The LTE-Tillage (50.660° N, 4.727° E) was established in 2005 with the initial aim of evaluating the effects of different modes of tillage within the specific context of the silt loam region.

Since the start of the trial, the field is cultivated using a two-year crop rotation, starting with sugar beet followed by winter wheat except in 2010, 2014 when flax (*Linum usitatissimum* L.) and in 2018 maize (*Zea mays* L.) were cultivated.

The trial compares four contrasting treatments of soil tillage, implemented within plots measuring 21 m x 12 m. These treatments are replicated four times, following a Latin square design with the blocks aligned in a row. Each of the 16 plots are 2 times subdivided following a split-split design. These factors are :

- Control/TMS (a mineral fertilizer) : not considered in the present study
- Non treated/Treated with a fungicide product (only for winter wheat)

The tillage treatments compared are as follows :

- Conventional tillage (CT) : inversion tillage with a plough, 25-30 cm deep
- NIT (Non-Inversion Tillage) : non-inversion tillage with a subsoiler, 30-35 cm deep
- RT_1 (Reduced tillage) : non-inversion tillage with a stubble harrow, 12 cm deep
- RT_2 (Reduced tillage) : non-inversion tillage with a stubble harrow, 12 cm deep

Note that the RT treatments although currently considered as identical, have different soil tillage histories as RT_2 was ploughed annually between 2005 and 2009.

The management of organic matters is equivalent to that of the RR + CC treatment in the LTE-OM.

Various cover crops have been cultivated since the start of the experiment, with phacelia having been grown most frequently (6 years), followed by mustard (3 years), clover (3 years) and oat (1 year).

2.2. Yield stability indices

In the review article of Reckling et al. 2021, a methodological guide has been proposed to aid in the evaluation of yield stability in agricultural LTEs as there are currently no commonly accepted guidelines or consensus for assessing yield stability in LTEs. Currently, there exists a list of 42 stability indices. Some of them are mathematically equivalent or correlate strongly with other indices. Our initial objective was to interpret the results of various indices while considering different characteristics : static vs dynamic, variance-based vs regression-based.

When analyzing the stability of yields, it is important to consider that different stability measures may lead to contrasting conclusions, partly because they reflect different concepts of stability, making the interpretation difficult. Furthermore, the choice of stability index has to be specific to the LTE since they are characterized by a number of typical issues that affect stability analysis in specific ways.

In our two case-studies, these indices were initially selected : Coefficient of variation (CV, static and variance-based), Regression coefficient against environmental mean (FW, dynamic and regression-based) and Power Law Residuals (POLAR, static and regression-based).

CV is defined as the ratio between the standard deviation and the mean according to eq. (1) :

$$CV = \frac{\sigma}{\mu} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where (σ is estimated by the standard deviation (SD, kg/ha) and μ is estimated by the mean yield (kg/ha). CV is expressed as a percentage.

A high CV indicates that the group is more variable, whereas a low value indicates greater stability. This metric was calculated for each crop x treatment x year combination.

In a data set generating variances σ^2 and means μ , such as an LTE, variances may depend on the means in a systematic way. The British ecologist Lionel Roy Taylor found that numerous insect populations could well be described by the equation : $\log(\sigma^2) = \log(a) + b \log(\mu)$, or expressed differently, $\sigma^2 = a\mu^b$ (Reckling et al., 2022). Later research demonstrated that this power relationship between variance and mean, termed Taylor's power law (TPL) is extremely widespread, and Döring et al. (2015) showed that this dependence can also be found to hold in crop yield data.

However, if such dependence is so widespread, i.e. if it is generally observed, no matter what data set, this may be seen to be problematic for yield stability analysis. For example, it can be shown that if TPL holds and $b < 2$, the coefficient of variation (CV) generally decreases in a non-linear way with increasing mean μ (Döring & Reckling 2018). If this is principally the case, it is not convincing to interpret a low CV value of a particular treatment as high stability when in fact the main reason is a high mean value of this treatment. In other words, if TPL holds, and regularly so, there may not be any genuine information on stability in the data that is not already contained in the mean.

To deal with a possible TPL in our LTE data analysis, we have plotted $\log(\sigma^2)$ against $\log(\mu)$ of yields and statistically tested the linear dependence between these two variables. The stability results can then be discussed in the light of the potential TPL dependence and the slope b of the relationship between $\log(\sigma^2)$ against $\log(\mu)$.

In the case where TPL holds, the POLAR values were according to :

$$u_i = \log(\sigma^2) - (a + b \times \log(\mu))$$

with u_i , the residuals of the TPL's regression line; a and b , the regression parameters (y-intercept and the slope, respectively)

We can interpret a low POLAR value as a high stability, whereas a high value corresponds to a low stability.

Thirdly, a regression-based indicator has been calculated following Finlay and Wilkinson (1963) to assess the interaction between the yield performances of a single crop within a treatment in relation to the mean yield of this crop over all treatments. In this regression analyses, annual yields of individual treatments were plotted against the mean annual yields of all treatments included in the comparison to be interpreted as an indicator of environmental adaptability. The performance of an individual treatment is evaluated by comparing the slope of the regression lines (FW, Finlay-Wilkinson regression coefficient b_i) independent of the intercept. A positive slope value greater than one ($b > 1$) indicates higher environmental adaptability. Higher environmental adaptability means that favorable environmental conditions result in higher yields. A slope value lower than one ($b < 1$) indicates a lower environmental adaptability.

We also used the R package toolStability (Wang et al. 2019) to compute the following stability measures : (1) safety-first index (Eskridge 1990), (2) coefficient of determination (Pinthus, 1973), (3) coefficient of regression (Finlay and Wilkinson, 1963), (4) deviation mean squares (Eberhart and Russell, 1966), (5) environmental variance (Roemer 1917), (6) genotypic stability (Hanson 1970), (7) genotypic superiority measure (Lin and Binns 1988), (8) variance of rank (Nassar and Huehn 1987), (9) stability variance (Shukla 1972), (10) adjusted coefficient of variation (Döring and Reckling 2018) and (11) ecovalence (Wricke 1962). These indices were calculated at plot levels across environments (years) and are presented as preliminary results in table C5.

The safety-first index was reused to plot the probability that the yield of each crop x treatment combination falls below various thresholds according to the risk-based approach (Eskridge, 1990). The advantage of this method is that it considers both variability and mean in a very direct and meaningful way at the same time (Reckling et al., 2021).

Given that the redundancy of the results obtained with the methods of CV, POLAR, Finlay-wilkinson regression and risk-based approach, only the results of CV are presented and discussed in this report. The graphs and values of the other stability parameters are presented in Appendix C.

2.3. Climate extremes

To identify climate extremes during the growing seasons of the main crops, degree-days ($^{\circ}$ C) and cumulative rainfall (mm) were estimated. These calculations were tailored to each crop's specific growing season and climatic requirements. The degree-days quantify the accumulation of heat or cold over time, which influences the growth and development of crops, while cumulative rainfall was measured to assess water availability.

Daily climate data were sourced from the AGRI4CAST dataset provided by the Joint Research Centre (JRC). This dataset includes historical meteorological data from 1979 onwards. To capture climate extremes, the 10th and 90th percentiles of the indicators were calculated. These percentiles were used as thresholds to define extreme conditions:

- Extreme cold or insufficient heat: Defined by daily degree day values falling below the 10th percentile.
- Extreme heat: Defined by daily degree day values exceeding the 90th percentile.
- Drought extremes: Defined by cumulative rainfall values below the 10th percentile.
- Rainfall extremes: Defined by cumulative rainfall values above the 90th percentile.

These percentile thresholds were calculated separately for each crop's growing requirements.

2.4. Impact of climate extremes on yield levels and yield stability

Climate stress effects and their interaction with treatment effects on yield levels and yield stability (CV) were assessed with linear mixed models. Datasets for each crop and individual climate stress event (drought, excessive rainfalls, cold and heat extremes) were clustered into two groups: normal years and years under climate stress.

Given the observed strong influence of time on the crop yields (Fig. 1) and the limited number of years of climatic stress selected, we identified a potential for bias when conducting pairwise comparisons between the normal and climate-stressed years. This concern is particularly true for heat waves, which occurred from the 2000s when crop yields were significantly higher due

to the continuous improvement of agricultural practices, particularly in plant breeding, fertilization and crop protection (Mba et al., 2012). In order to avoid this bias, yields were time-detrended by subtracting the overall year effect from yield values.

2.5. Statistical analyses

All statistical analyses were made by using R software : for the mixed models *lme4* and *multcomp* packages. Treatments (factorial), years (numerical) were considered as fixed factors, replications (or blocks) were considered as random factors.

3. Results

3.1. Crop yields

Fig. 1. Evolution of mean crop yields in each treatment of the LTE-OM across the years. A : sugar beet, B : winter wheat, C : winter barley

Fig. 2. Evolution of mean crop yield in each factor of the LTE-Tillage across the years. A : sugar beet - soil tillage, B1 : winter wheat - soil tillage, B2 : winter wheat - fungicides

In figures 1 and 2, the mean annual yields of the different main crops are presented per year and per treatment in the LTE-OM and LTE-Tillage, respectively.

It is observed that there are statistically highly significant differences ($p < 0.001$) among the years for all crops except for the winter wheat of the LTE-Tillage (Table 1).

The organic matter management practices significantly affected, though to a lesser extent than years, the yields of winter wheat ($p = 0.02$) and winter barley ($p < 0.001$). However, these practices did not had a significant impact on sugar beet yields.

In treatments receiving livestock manures inputs (CM, PS + RR + CC_1 and 2), winter barley yields were significantly higher than those in the control treatment (RE), exhibiting average relative differences of 10,7% ($p = 0.004$), 11,7% ($p = 0.001$), and 10,2 % ($p = 0.009$), respectively. The RR and RR + CC treatments yielded intermediate results with no significant differences compared to other treatments.

For winter wheat, the yield differences reflected those observed in winter barley, though only PS + RR + CC_1 and CM were significantly higher than RE, with average relative differences of 6,5% ($p = 0.005$) and 5,4% ($p = 0.035$), respectively. Additionally, the PS + RR + CC_1 treatment outperformed the RR treatment, with a relative difference of 5,2% ($p = 0.044$).

Soil tillage treatments had no significant effect on the yields of sugar beets or winter wheat. However, the application of fungicides strongly affected the yields of winter wheat ($p < 0.001$) that were consistently higher in treated plots showing a positive difference of 9,5% compared to the untreated plots.

Table 1. Analysis of Variance Table. Response variable : Crop yield

Experiment	Crop	Factors	F	df	Pr(>F)
LTE-OM	Sugar beet	Treatment	0.65	5	0.663

		Year	345.82	1	< 0.001 ***
	Winter wheat	Treatment	3.76	5	0.002 **
		Year	1268.79	1	< 0.001 ***
	Winter barley	Treatment	4.69	5	< 0.001 ***
		Year	376.74	1	< 0.001 ***
LTE-Tillage	Sugar beet	Soil tillage	0.97	3	0.408
		Crop protection	2.14	1	0.146
		Year	71.72	1	< 0.001 ***
	Winter wheat	Soil tillage	0.03	3	0.992
		Crop protection	78.70	1	< 0.001 ***
		Year	2.61	1	0.107

3.2. Yield stability

Fig. 3. Evolution of coefficient of variation (CV) in each treatment of LTE-OM across the years. A : sugar beet, B : winter wheat, C : winter barley

Fig. 4. Evolution of coefficient of variation (CV) in each factor of LTE-Tillage across the years. A : sugar beet - soil tillage, B1 : winter wheat - soil tillage, B2 : winter wheat - crop protection

In figures 3 and 4, the CVs of crop yields are presented per year and per treatment in LTE-OM and LTE-Tillage, respectively.

The ANOVA (Table 2) results indicate that the year had a significant impact on the CV for winter wheats in both experiments and for sugar beet in the LTE-OM but not in the LTE-Tillage. Treatment effects were not significant for any of the crops studied.

Table 2. Analysis of Variance Table. Response variable : Coefficient of variation

Experiment	Crop	Factors	F	df	Pr(>F)
LTE-OM	Sugar beet	Treatment	0.62	5	0.687
		Year	11.20	1	0.001 **
	Winter wheat	Treatment	1.75	5	0.13
		Year	67.53	1	0.035 *
	Winter barley	Treatment	0.28	5	0.921
		Year	0.62	1	0.434
LTE-Tillage	Sugar beet	Soil tillage	0.11	3	0.95
		Crop protection	0.24	1	0.629
		Year	0.03	1	0.865
	Winter wheat	Treatment	0.22	3	0.882
		Crop protection	0.06	1	0.811
		Year	13.03	1	< 0.001 ***

3.3. Climate extremes

For the period 1979 to 2023, threshold values obtained to define extreme climate years (extreme cold, heat, drought and rainfalls) of each crop growing season are presented in Tables B1 and B2. Figures B1 to B4 illustrate the crop-specific stressed growing seasons identified for temperature and rainfalls extremes within the two LTEs, along with the corresponding crop rotations. Given that only one main crop is cultivated each year in both LTEs, some years of stress could not be exploited.

In this study, the minimum criteria for evaluating the effects of each extreme climate event on crop yields and yield stability required a minimum of two years of identified stresses. Tables B1 and B2 detail the years selected for each crop x stress event in the LTE-OM and the LTE-Tillage, respectively.

In the LTE-OM, we were able to assess the impact of cold years on sugar beet, heat and drought on winter wheat and barley and excessive rainfalls on winter wheat.

The same data and thresholds were used for the LTE-Tillage; however, due to differences in crop rotation and the more recent establishment of this experiment compared to LTE-OM, fewer years of climate extremes could be selected. Specifically we could only evaluate the effects of extreme heat years on sugar beet within this context.

3.4. Yield under climatic stress

All cropping seasons under climatic stress, with the exception of cold cropping seasons ($p = 0.549$, Table 3) significantly influenced crop yields (residuals after time-detrending).

The most significant effect of climate stress was observed during wet cropping seasons, that led to a depressive effect of -15,2% on winter wheat yields ($p < 0.001$). Interestingly, both drought and heat stresses exhibited positive effects, which was more significant for drought resulting in respective yield increases of 11,4% and 9,1% for winter wheat and winter barley ($p < 0.001$). Moreover, hot cropping seasons also induced higher relative yields, with increases of 5,1 % for winter wheat ($p = 0.001$) and barley ($p = 0.003$), and of 4,8% for sugar beet ($p = 0.021$).

Treatment effects were more significant in the 1979-2023 period compared to the overall period (Table 1) which was expected given the detrending of the year effect. Additionally, in the LTE-OM the comparison between treatments in the 1979-2023 time serie were made two decades after the establishment of the experiment and it is well documented (Poulton et al., 2018) that the positive impact of organic fertilization requires time to significantly affect soil properties and subsequently crop yields.

So the matter of interest here is the interaction effect between climatic stresses and treatments which was only significant for the interaction with drought ($p < 0.001$) and heat ($p = 0.034$) induced-stress on winter barley. In comparison with normal years where differences in crop yields were only significant between treatments receiving livestock manures (PS + RR + CC and CM) and the control, in hot cropping seasons, livestock manure treatments demonstrated even higher relative increases than the control and RR treatments, with relative increases of 16-18% for PS + RR + CC and 20% for CM. During drought years, only the application of pig slurry in the PS + RR + CC treatments resulted in significantly higher relative yields than in normal conditions, with increases of 16% to 25% compared to the control. Furthermore, in comparison with normal years, the yield difference between the CM treatment and the control was not significant.

Table 3. Analysis of Variance Table. Response variable : Crop yield (time-detrended)

Experiment	Crop	Climatic stress	Factors	Chisq	df	Pr (>Chisq)
LTE-OM	Sugar beet	Cold	Treatment	11.81	5	0.038 *
			Cold	0.36	1	0.549
			Treatment:Cold	9.51	5	0.090
	Winter wheat	Heat	Treatment	29.99	5	< 0.001 ***
			Heat	10.28	1	0.001 **
			Treatment:Heat	1.79	5	0.878
		Drought	Treatment	32.71	5	< 0.001 ***
			Drought	55.95	1	< 0.001 ***
			Treatment:Drought	1.76	5	0.881
		Wet	Treatment	34.34	5	< 0.001 ***
			Wet	97.83	1	< 0.001 ***
			Treatment:Wet	2.73	5	0.741
	Winter barley	Heat	Treatment	39.94	5	< 0.001 ***
			Heat	9.10	1	0.003 **
			Treatment:Heat	12.06	5	0.034 *
Drought		Treatment	43.77	5	< 0.001 ***	
		Drought	33.60	1	< 0.001 ***	
		Treatment:Drought	22.64	5	< 0.001 ***	
LTE-Tillage	Sugar beet	Heat	Soil tillage	4.20	3	0.240
			Heat	5.30	1	0.021 *
			Soil tillage:Heat	4.22	3	0.239

3.5. Yield stability under climatic stress

Only the CV of winter barley yield was affected by climatic stress. Hot cropping seasons induced a higher CV and so a lower stability, with a positive difference of 7% ($p < 0.001$, Table 4) compared to normal years. In the opposite, drought cropping seasons resulted in a lower CV, with a negative difference of 3% ($p = 0.02$) compared to normal years.

None of the treatments demonstrated a significant effect on CV, whether cropping seasons were normal or under climatic stress.

Table 4 : Analysis of Variance Table. Response variable : Coefficient of variation

Experiment	Crop	Climatic stress	Factors	F	df	Pr(>F)
LTE-OM	Sugar beet	Cold	Treatment	0.46	5	0.815
			Cold	0.04	1	0.836
			Treatment:Cold	0.22	5	0.954
	Winter wheat	Heat	Treatment	1.47	5	0.209
			Heat	0.29	1	0.592

		Drought	Treatment:Heat	0.08	5	0.996
			Treatment	1.49	5	0.205
			Drought	0.83	1	0.365
		Treatment:Drought	0.12	5	0.988	
		Wet	Treatment	1.52	5	0.195
			Wet	0.44	1	0.511
	Treatment:Wet		0.49	5	0.784	
	Winter barley	Heat	Treatment	0.71	5	0.615
			Heat	37.74	1	< 0.001 ***
			Treatment:Heat	1.00	5	0.424
		Drought	Treatment	0.46	5	0.801
			Drought	5.70	1	0.02 *
Treatment:Drought			0.61	5	0.694	
LTE-Tillage	Sugar beet	Heat	Soil tillage	0.73	3	0.56
			Heat	0.03	1	0.87
			Soil tillage:Heat	0.04	3	0.99

4. Discussion and conclusion

The results from the LTE-OM and LTE-Tillage highlight that soil and crop management practices predominantly influenced crop yield levels rather than yield stability.

Our analysis revealed that the applications of livestock manures had a more pronounced effect on yields, especially for winter cereals (wheat and barley), whereas the effects of soil tillage was found to be not significant. Within the LTE-Tillage, only the crop protection factor was significant for winter wheat, with anticipated increased crop yields in plots where fungicides were applied.

Throughout the overall experimental period, yield stability remained unaffected by any treatments. The variations of CV across environments (years) was dependent on the crops evaluated. Notably, the CV tended to increase over time for winter wheat, while the time-response for sugar beet were inconsistent between the two LTEs.

Interestingly, climatic stress events (extreme drought, rainfalls, heat and cold) affected both yield and yield stability. These effects were also more pronounced on crop yield rather than on yield stability.

In terms of yield, the effect size of the stresses were in descending order : a depressive effect of wet cropping seasons on winter wheat, positive effects of drought on winter cereals and heat on all evaluated crops. Additionally, comparisons of treatment effects between normal and climate-stressed growing seasons indicated that the application of livestock manures allowed to reach relatively higher yields for winter barley compared to mineral fertilized plots in hot and drought years. Moreover, in drought years, only the use of pig slurry led to significantly higher yields while the application of cattle manures showed no such effect.

These results suggest that the application of livestock manures contributes to a more resilient cropping system under climate-stressed conditions. However, the overall impact of organic matter inputs must be interpreted with caution; significant effects during climate-stressed

growing seasons were observed only for winter barley, which is cultivated every three years in the LTE-OM.

Regarding yield stability, the influence of the treatments under climate stress was small, again significant only for winter barley. Our findings presented opposite outcomes under drought and heat stresses, with higher yield stability in one case and a lower stability in the other case.

One major limitation of this study is the relatively small number of observations with climatic stress events, especially for LTE-Tillage. While yield and yield stability seem to be affected by organic fertilization in the LTE-OM under climatic stress, it is important to note that the available dataset for LTE-Tillage was substantially smaller, which explains the relatively fewer climate stress events analyzed in relation to soil tillage management and crop protection. Furthermore, more precise identification of climatic stress is required, utilizing standardized indicators calculated specifically for each crop during critical phenological stages for yield establishment, rather than over the entire cropping season.

Consequently, the conclusions drawn from this study should be regarded as preliminary. Further research with extended duration and additional variables will be necessary to ascertain treatment and environmental effects on yield and yield stability.

5. Supplementary material

Appendix A : Evolution of experimental protocol in the LTE-OM

Fig. A1. Evolution of the protocole for the six treatments in

Fig. B1. Rainfalls-induced stresses throughout the 1979-2023 period, specific to the cropping seasons of the main crops within the LTE-OM. The list of crops presented above the figure corresponds to the crop succession in the LTE. The years selected for the analysis of each crop are framed in bold.

Table B1. Years and threshold values of each climatic stress (drought, wet, cold and heat years) for each main crop of the LTE-OM. The years selected for the analysis are in bold. The minimum criteria is that number of years ≥ 2 .

Crop	Average Growing seasons	Number of growing seasons	Climate stress	Threshold value	Years of climatic stress
Sugar beet	04/01 – 11/01	12	Cold	< 1877 °C.day	1984, 1991
			Heat	> 2248 °C.day	2006
			Drought	< 294 mm	1991
			Wet	> 541 mm	2000
Winter wheat	11/01 – 08/01	16	Cold	< 2142 °C.day	1985
			Heat	> 2711 °C.day	1995, 2022
			Drought	< 473 mm	1989, 2022
			Wet	> 686 mm	1995, 2016
Winter barley	10/01 – 07/01	12	Cold	< 2018 °C.day	1986
			Heat	> 2524 °C.day	2014, 2020, 2023
			Drought	< 477 mm	1990, 1993, 1996, 2017
			Wet	> 690 mm	/

Fig. B3. Temperature-induced stresses throughout the 2005-2023 period, specific to the cropping seasons of the main crops within the LTE-Tillage. The list of crops presented above the figure corresponds to the crop succession in the LTE. The stresses are framed in bold when there is a correspondance with the crop succession.

Fig. B4. Rainfalls-induced stresses throughout the 2005-2023 period, specific to the cropping seasons of the main crops within the LTE-Tillage. The list of crops presented above the figure corresponds to the crop succession in the LTE. The stresses are framed in bold when there is a correspondance with the crop succession.

Table B2. Years and treshold values of each climatic stress (drought, wet, cold and heat years) for each main crop of the LTE-Tillage. The years selected for the analysis are in bold. The minimum criteria is that number of years ≥ 2 .

Crop	Average Growing seasons	Number of growing seasons	Climate stress	Treshold value	Years of climatic stress
Sugar beet	04/01 – 11/01	6	Cold	< 1877 °C.day	/
			Heat	> 2248 °C.day	2006, 2020, 2022
			Drought	< 294 mm	2022
			Wet	> 541 mm	2008
Winter wheat	11/01 – 08/01	9	Cold	< 2142 °C.day	/
			Heat	> 2711 °C.day	2007
			Drought	< 473 mm	2017
			Wet	> 686 mm	2021

Appendix C : Visualization of other yield stability parameters

Fig. C1. Linear regression between the mean annual yield and treatment yield per year for each main crop of the LTE-OM. A : sugar beet, B : winter wheat, C : winter barley

Fig. C2. Linear regression between the mean annual yield and treatment yield per year for each main crop of the LTE-Tillage. A : sugar beet – soil tillage, B1 : winter wheat – soil tillage, B2 : winter wheat – crop protection

Fig. C3. Yield risk comparison of organic fertilization treatments over a range of threshold values for each main crop of the LTE-OM. A : sugar beet, B : winter wheat, C : winter barley

Fig. C4. Yield risk comparison of organic fertilization treatments over a range of threshold values for each main crop of the LTE-Tillage. A : sugar beet – soil tillage, B1 : winter wheat – soil tillage, B2 : winter wheat – crop protection

Table C5. Stability indices of crop x treatment combination in the LTE-OM and LTE-Tillage. P = Safety first index, R² = Coefficient of determination, b = Regression coefficient against environmental mean, S²d = Deviation mean squares, D² = Genotypic stability, Pi = Genotypic superiority measure, Si = Variance of rank, σ² = Stability variance, aCV = Adjusted coefficient of variation, Wi = Ecovalence

LTE	Crop	Treatment	Mean Yield	POLAR	P	R ²	b	S ² d	Environmental variance	D ²	Pi	Si	σ ²	aCV	Wi	Ecovalence modified
LTE-OM	Sugar beet	RE	9564	0.069	0.500	0.89	1.00	1030454	8981884	115167730	3143797	105	1232650	30.82	109228651	1011376
		PS + RR + CC_1	9955	0.048	0.444	0.86	0.92	1101572	7831188	115675398	2440599	118	1413123	29.36	120961253	1130479
		PS + RR + CC_2	9606	-0.146	0.494	0.91	0.92	662421	7405560	62267597	2294649	96	767052	28.04	67490822	703029
		CM	9915	0.042	0.458	0.91	1.12	940745	10888545	134419677	2186854	109	1268778	34.55	111805746	1035238
		RR	9346	0.005	0.527	0.90	1.08	1095905	10444242	123230267	2579020	94	1405127	32.85	107902238	1123982
		RR + CC	9652	-0.033	0.487	0.89	0.95	903223	7994812	96403651	3089598	101	1079488	29.21	98303106	910214
	Winter wheat	RE	7176	0.030	0.543	0.91	0.92	216170	2509910	25075662	789695	104	282148	22.77	27323988	231559
		PS + RR + CC_1	7659	-0.241	0.429	0.94	1.03	178190	3077210	24956281	165413	103	201069	22.23	20999815	177965
		PS + RR + CC_2	7468	-0.049	0.473	0.94	1.06	178405	3222509	26893852	324595	101	209737	23.88	21675972	183695
		CM	7558	-0.023	0.454	0.95	1.06	172340	3276996	26548114	331299	107	203616	23.53	21017336	179635
		RR	7288	0.000	0.514	0.93	0.95	193423	2613919	22937188	641949	94	230804	22.54	23518438	197634
		RR + CC	7355	0.286	0.498	0.87	0.99	387289	3018061	46945793	661629	101	508456	23.80	45360467	381180
LTE-Tillage	Sugar beet	RE	6397	-0.045	0.656	0.84	0.86	381128	2450480	32395921	1827922	114	520336	25.80	36927807	424458
		PS + RR + CC_1	7208	-0.046	0.462	0.88	1.08	424102	3655925	47134583	564806	108	530149	25.78	37490436	430925
		PS + RR + CC_2	7136	0.017	0.478	0.89	1.09	415243	3868760	44494792	709422	101	523628	26.97	34527029	426260
		CM	7134	-0.076	0.478	0.92	1.09	288761	3613286	37238090	556868	99	340216	26.08	26600900	305757
		RR	6699	0.087	0.574	0.84	0.95	499444	3133388	41193734	1542731	108	627703	27.00	40077658	494786
		RR + CC	6942	0.070	0.521	0.87	0.93	359878	2787014	31811721	896871	99	428053	23.98	31636923	363643
	Winter wheat	CT	11288	-	0.473	0.57	0.95	1509196	3514692	100234562	3869438	286	1763130	15.58	99953887	1469910
		NIT	11371	-	0.466	0.47	1.04	3320848	6244366	250672681	4443658	252	5342359	19.91	246109738	3238286
		RT_1	11205	-	0.491	0.54	1.01	1569038	3434714	67075838	3569935	427	1844775	16.08	65904868	1497838
		RT_2	10701	-	0.615	0.59	0.89	1017264	2466914	42725108	5055402	309	814278	17.77	43749172	994299
		CT	9701	-	0.525	0.77	1.00	379604	1644834	57847705	643274	382	545296	12.53	56943425	374628
		NIT	9722	-	0.520	0.84	0.99	238614	1477809	36439320	542729	233	265263	11.95	35800957	235533
Winter wheat	RT_1	9950	-	0.445	0.77	1.00	325221	1444811	38993834	709194	287	436075	12.60	38377326	319811	
	RT_2	9985	-	0.429	0.76	0.93	314732	1286947	37138333	682125	315	424738	12.01	37702758	314190	
	NT	9441	-	0.685	0.89	0.93	118877	1086447	26390757	1261419	321	0	11.23	27570248	123081	
	T	10378	-	0.357	0.91	1.07	128950	1403861	33344855	241380	365	Inf	11.23	29806383	133064	

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